

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A577

18 September 1997

ACSOE

Intercomparison flight with NOAA P3

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 577

DATE: 18 19 197

Take off: 1100

Landing: 1900

Aircraft Scientist : A. KATE

Flight Leader : I. RUIE

Others ECHL : J. KENT

PSAP' EIZ : K. DEWEY

BOTTLES : D. ALTHAM

PENETA : T. GREEN

FORMALDHYDE : G. WILLS

PEROXIDE : B. DANDY

CO : S. SCHMITZEN

NOx-1 : S. BAUGVITTE

Captain : C. O'BRIEN

Co-pilot : M. PORSE

Navigator : J. AYRES

Engineer : M. LEMMINGS

Loadmaster : K. QUICK

+ K. LAW

C. REEVES

S. PENKETT

Trials Instructions MRF 1 : ACSOE

Operating area : N. ATLANTIC

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A577, 18th September, 1997
 ACSOE Intercomparison with the P3
 North Atlantic near the Azores

Start time	End time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
105835					Take off St Maria
111311	112419	R1	FL80	315°	
134301	140001	R2	FL200	200°	
140001	140651	P1	FL200 FL140	010°	
140801	142301	R3	FL140	010°	
142301	143039	P2	FL140 FL70	200°	
143401	144901	R4	FL70	210°	
144901	145608	P3	FL70 1000'	015°	
145701	151501	R5	1000'	015°	
151817	152837	P4.1	50' FL100	310°	
153003	153257	R6	FL100	180°	
153227	154433	P4.2	FL100 FL200	170°	
155714	162652	P5	FL200 5000'	175°	Bottles filled @ FL185, FL165,FL88,5000'
163043	165231	P6	5000' FL200	170°	Bottles filled @ FL85, FL165,FL200
165817	172953	P7	FL200 2000'	170°	Bottles filled @ FL180, FL164,FL120,FL50,2000'
173141	175657	P8	2000' FL250	130°	Bottles filled @ FL150, FL237,FL250
180102	181443	P9	FL250 FL110	135°	Bottles filled @ FL210, FL110
181838	183025	R7	FL110	135°	
190034					Land St Maria

A577

September 18, 1997

ACSOE C-130 P3 Intercomparison Flight

SORTIE OBJECTIVE:

Version 1.0

To compare atmospheric chemistry measurements made by the MRF C-130 aircraft with those made by the NOAA P-3 aircraft.

LOCATION: North Atlantic Ocean, Northwest of the Azores.

WEATHER: Cloud Free

FLIGHT PATTERN:

- [1] Depart Santa Maria.
 - [1.1] Hold climb at 3000 ft for wet chemistry check.
- [2] Standard climb to FL080.
 - [2.1] Run for NOxy Calibration (15 min).
- [3] Standard climb and transit to operational area as convenient
- [4] Rendezvous with NOAA P-3. **44N 35W FL200 13:30 UTC**
Operational axis 40-44 N 35W
- [5] Straight and level run at FL200(15 minutes). **Bottle filling:**
- [6] Profile descent from FL200 to FL140 — 1000ft/min. **During Intercomparison:**
- [7] Straight and level run at FL140 (15 minutes). Use MRF bottles.
- [8] Reciprocal turn onto reverse track
- [9] Profile descent from FL140 to FL70 — 1000ft/min. Fill two bottles per straight and level run. Second bottle fill to be complete 1 minute before end of run to allow for instrument zeroes.
- [10] Straight and level run at FL70(15 minutes).
- [11] Profile descent from FL70 to 1000ft — 1000ft/min. **During sawtooth:**
- [12] Straight and level run at 1000ft (15 minutes). Fill one bottle per step.
- [13] Profile ascent from 1000ft to FL100 — 1000ft/min.
- [14] Break formation with NOAA P-3.
- [15] Stepped Sawtooth back towards Santa Maria between: _____ and _____.
Filling bottles at: _____, _____, _____, _____.
- [16] Straight and level run for NOxy Calibration (15 min)
and possible NOxy shutdown (20 min).
- [17] Return to Santa Maria.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS:

Cabin pressure and temperature to be kept constant on level runs. The NOxy should ideally be zeroed every 15 minutes. During profiles this should be done at the start of grab sample runs. Other instrument operators should perform zeros at this time if required.

TIME: 8 hours.

6:45 Ground Crew and Instrument Transport

8:30 Science and sortie brief

10:15 All observers on C-130

8:45 Air Crew Transport

11:00 T/O

A577 ACSOE SCIENCE

September 18, 1997

MRC C-130 — NOAA P-3 Intercomparison

Aircraft Scientist Debrief:

Weather:

The operating area was chosen to the Northwest of Santa Maria. The operational axis (40-44°N, 35°W) was just to the east of a frontal system and trough. There was very little cloud at the southern end of the axis, getting more complex and cloudy to the north. This did not pose a problem because we operated from FL200 at the northern end, and flew at lower levels to the southern end of the axis.

Instrumentation:

Because of the required co-ordination with the NOAA P-3 the takeoff time was not flexible. The NOxy instrument had a major failure of the NO₂ channel on initial powerup. This was rectified by replumbing the instrument to enable the spare Noy channel to be used for NO₂. The HORACE software had to be reconfigured in flight to accomodate these changes and rescale the Formaldehyde.

Overview:

This was a successful intercomparison sortie. The mission scientists were very pleased with the data collected during the flight, and reams of plots were printed. We successfully rendezvoused with the P-3 as planned and executed the intercomparison exactly as planned.

The aircrew set up the radios so that the aircrew had one radio frequency, and the Scientists had a separate channel (123.45) to discuss the science. This enabled us to co-ordinate the science without interfering with the pilots.

During the straight and level runs, the C-130 formed on the P-3. The P-3 then formed on us, joining us as we profiled from 50ft to FL100.

We then sawtoothed back to Santa Maria. It had been hoped to sawtooth between FL80 and FL250, however we were not able to get ATC clearance to climb above FL200 until the final sawtooth. Due to the short track length available for the final profile, it was decided to climb at 1,500 ft/min because the Mission scientists were more interested in the upper levels.

25 bottles were filled during the flight, 9 during the intercomparison and the remaining 16 during the sawtooth back to base.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kurye*

Project: ACSOE P3-INT.

Flight No: *A577*

Date: 18/9/97

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529-874
Sooty
554-absorb
536-trans.

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:06:30	Trans.	3200 ^{Pres} Rad FL	299	37.11 -25.57	3/8 cu below. some thin sc, clear above. very good visibility.
11:11:07	R15	80 ^{Pres} Rad FL	299	37.23 -25.77	8/8 sc below clear above 11:13:11
11:24:19	R1e	79 ^{Pres} Rad FL	304	37.75 -26.84	8/8 sc some gaps ahead. Ilos de Pico visible ahead through the clouds.
11:35:51	TRANS	90 ^{Pres} Rad FL	296	38.09 -27.52	6/8 sc below thin Pico visible clearly ^{above} through the clouds good visibility, clear above.
11:50:36	TRANSIT	180 ^{Pres} Rad FL	303	38.54 -28.66	6/8 sc below. some cu breaking through. good visibility and no cloud above.
12:10:29	TRANSIT	180 ^{Pres} Rad FL	294	39.21 -30.50	Flocks just ahead. Scattered cu below. Small cu fields visible. Clear above?
12:28:44	TRANSIT	180 ^{Pres} Rad FL	330	40.20 -31.74	4/8 broken sc sheets below. large clear areas of surface visible.
12:46:20	TRANSIT	180 ^{Pres} Rad FL	325	41.38 -32.59	5/8 sc below. some fields of small cu. some ci ahead.
12:56:00	TRANSIT	180 ^{Pres} Rad FL	325	42.03 -33.13	7/8 sc below. some ci ahead.
		^{Pres} Rad FL			
		^{Pres} Rad FL			

NOAA42

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: ACSOE P3-int
Flight No: A577

Date: 18/9/97
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1300
1355

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13:22:44		Pres Rad FL			Contact made with NOAA P3 VHF 2 - Scientist Radio.
13:24:30	TRANSIT	180 Pres Rad FL	313		Solid cloud below it appears to be be heavier some ci above
13:35		Pres Rad FL			contact w/ ^{13:45-59:} @ 13:45-59: 15-8 -24.6 210/27 Kts p. 466.2 mb.
14:06:01		Pres Rad FL			Amin → 13:56 bottle fill 13:59 START OF PROFILE.
		Pres Rad FL			14:08:01 → Start of Run
		Pres Rad FL			14:10 - 14:15 hydro carb.
		Pres Rad FL			Bottle fill at 14:12:00
		Pres Rad FL			14:23: 21-22
		Pres Rad FL			14:14 → = 25. -33.6 WD 20.6 Sb: 595.3 22 Kts
		Pres Rad FL			Na ₂ and ozone Ozone in: @ 25 ppb
		Pres Rad FL			Small CO ← 14:17:54
		Pres Rad FL			

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye.*

Project: *ACSOE P-3*

Flight No: *A577*

Date: *18/9/97*

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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
<i>[4:25:21]</i>		Pres Rad FL			<i>Start of profile end of run end of run profile at 14:30:39. Some big cu ahead, but also some gaps.</i>
		Pres Rad FL			<i>E 70 Run start: 13:34:00 Hydro carbons: 40-45 Zeroed: 14:36 finish</i>
		Pres Rad FL			<i>14:36 → 8.4 c 1.8 W 208 / 15.9 Kts 782.1 NOAA Parameters.</i>
		Pres Rad FL			<i>14:37:17 - bottle filled.</i>
		Pres Rad FL			<i>14:41:00 Second bottle. Synchronized with their bottle filled</i>
<i>14:43:03</i>	<i>R-3</i>	<i>70</i>	<i>186</i>	<i>42.96 -35.89</i>	<i>ci above - 1/8 broken cu below. large cu ahead -</i>
		Pres Rad FL			<i>(49) end of run at 14:49:00</i>
		Pres Rad FL			<i>less variation in O₂ & NO₂ → lower</i>
		Pres Rad FL			<i>1000 ft P3 em 14:56:08.</i>

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist:

A. Kays

Project: ACSOE PS int.

Date: 18/9/97

Flight No: A577

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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		Pres Rad FL			14:57:01 start of Run
		Pres Rad FL			14:58:00 Zero. for instruments
		Pres Rad FL			Hydrocarbon → 15:15
		Pres Rad FL			19.5 15:04:34 19.5 18.0 19.8 17.2 kts 976. bank
		Pres Rad FL			15:10 → 15:15 zero @ 15:13
		Pres Rad FL			<u>broken cu very sparse at this level.</u>
15:17:17 15:17:17	P4.1	50 Pres Rad FL	292	44.26 -36.78	1015 for 5 scattered cu. over broken cloud above
15:28:36	P4.1e B6	100 Pres Rad FL	292	44.66 -37.06	& Calibration Run. Solid Sc below clearing to north. some ci above.
15:32:57	P4.2 P4.2	100 Pres Rad FL	162	44.44 -37.00	
15:41:31	P4.2e	200 Pres Rad FL	151	43.84 -36.67	Some cu above 3/8 cu below with some thin sheets of Stratus

State of 03 & NOy bettering second than first lower for both

(17:2)

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Keye.*

Project: *ACSOE P3-int.* Date: *18/9/97*

Flight No: *A577*

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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)									
		Pres Rad FL												
<i>15:57:14</i>	<i>P5</i>	Pres Rad FL			<i>18000 185. ↑</i> <i>165.</i> <i>135. 1250</i> <i>120</i> <i>115.</i> <i>80</i>									
<i>16:01:57</i>	<i>P5 in</i>	185 Pres Rad FL	<i>257</i>	<i>42.88</i> <i>-35.02</i>	<i>5/8 sc below 4/8 ci above, broke cu below</i> <i>SL deck</i>									
<i>16:04:39</i>	<i>P5 cont</i>	185 Pres Rad FL			<i>complex cloud below 3/8 ci above.</i> <i>16 (15) 00</i> <i>4</i>									
<i>16:07:05</i>		165 Pres Rad FL			<i>16:01:18 FL 115 to this cloud layer</i> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;"><i>5000 ft</i> <i>low</i></div>									
<i>16:26:24</i>	<i>P5e</i>	50 Pres Rad FL	<i>158</i>	<i>41.61</i> <i>-34.90</i>	<i>7/8 cu below 4/8 ci above.</i>									
<i>16:30:33</i>	<i>P6</i>	50 Pres Rad FL	<i>154</i>	<i>41.43</i> <i>-34.74</i>	<i>16:35:57 Restart Profile FL 80 Bottle</i>									
		Pres Rad FL			<i>15800 — interrupt for bottle fill</i> <i>16:44:02 — Restart 164840</i>									
<i>16:52:33</i>	<i>P6e</i> <i>P7a</i>	200 Pres Rad FL	<i>153</i>	<i>40.52</i> <i>-33.90</i>	<i>hands of cu below total cover as than 1/8</i> <i>clear above</i> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;"><i>Noxy Shut Down</i> <table style="font-size: small; border-collapse: collapse;"><tr><td style="border-right: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"><i>12 min</i></td><td style="border-right: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"><i>15 min</i></td><td style="padding: 2px;"><i>10 any</i></td></tr><tr><td style="border-right: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"><i>low</i></td><td style="border-right: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"><i>low</i></td><td style="padding: 2px;"><i>any</i></td></tr><tr><td style="border-right: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"><i>Sum</i></td><td style="border-right: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;"><i>fact</i></td><td style="padding: 2px;"><i>any</i></td></tr></table></div>	<i>12 min</i>	<i>15 min</i>	<i>10 any</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>any</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>fact</i>	<i>any</i>
<i>12 min</i>	<i>15 min</i>	<i>10 any</i>												
<i>low</i>	<i>low</i>	<i>any</i>												
<i>Sum</i>	<i>fact</i>	<i>any</i>												
		Pres Rad FL			<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px; display: inline-block;"><i>16:59:00</i> <i>16:59:00</i></div>									
<i>16:54:17</i>	<i>P7 ↓</i>	200 Pres Rad FL	<i>154</i>	<i>39.99</i> <i>-33.63</i>	<i>170016 interrupt</i> <i>Restart Profile 170421</i> <i>180 5 → 90A</i> <i>120</i>									

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A. Kaye*

Project: ACSOG P3-int.

Date: 18/9/97

Flight No: *A577*

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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
<i>17:05:35</i> 17:05:35					<i>fields of small cu below</i> $\swarrow 120 \searrow 50 \text{ } \swarrow 50 \searrow$
					<i>FL164 interrupt profile to to fill bottle in interesting layer.</i> <i>Restart @ 17:09:32</i>
					<i>FL120 P7int 17:14:04 to fill bottle in intermediate layer.</i> <i>17:16:37 Restart.</i>
<i>17:23:28</i>	<i>P7int</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>117</i>	<i>38.83</i> <i>-32.39</i>	<i>2/8 cu below alot of active cu ahead with cumimbs.</i> <i>Clear above. 17:26:37 Restart after bottle fill. just 3evd</i>
<i>17:29:53</i>	<i>P7and</i>	<i>2000</i>	<i>116</i>	<i>38.69</i> <i>-31.93</i>	<i>clear above and below with a bank of cu ahead of</i>
<i>17:31:41</i>	<i>P8A</i>	<i>2000</i>	<i>115</i>	<i>38.67</i> <i>-31.87</i>	<i>1500 ft/min climb. 17:41:15 interrupt @ FL150 for Noxy 3000 zeroes.</i> <i>17:42:29 restart.</i>
					<i>[Video of clouds reflected on sea surface]</i>
					<i>FL180 reducing rate of climb to 1000 ft/min</i> <i>interrupt for bottle fill</i> <i>17:53:57 bottle filled @ F235</i>
<i>17:56:59</i>	<i>P8A and</i>	<i>250</i>	<i>117</i>	<i>38.04</i> <i>-29.99</i>	<i>sc sheets below and streaks of cu. P100 visible through</i> <i>Cloud to left. PERC A (all off in sample phase)</i> <i>at this altitude</i>
					<i>FL200 FL180 FL210 FL100</i>

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: *A Kaye*.

Project: *ACSOE INT*
Flight No: *4572*

Date: *18/19/92*
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Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				Longitude	
<i>18:03:00</i>	<i>B Fill</i>	<i>210</i> <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	<i>120</i>	<i>37.84</i> <i>-29.48</i>	<i>Bottle fill Broad sheets of sc below 5/8</i> <i>Small cu between sheets. 18:07:15 descent.</i>
	<i>P9 ↓</i>	<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			
<i>18:14:44</i>	<i>P.P. vend</i> <i>Bottle fill</i>	<i>110</i> <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	<i>116</i>	<i>37.50</i> <i>-28.63</i>	<i>clear below small cu field to right,</i> <i>layers of sc ahead, clear above.</i>
<i>18:18:38</i>	<i>R7</i>	<i>110</i> <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	<i>119</i>	<i>37.36</i> <i>-28.26</i>	<i>Noxy calibration run 12 min @ science speed.</i>
<i>18:30:20</i>	<i>R7e</i>	<i>110</i> <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	<i>94</i>	<i>37.16</i> <i>-27.40</i>	<i>END OF SCIENCE</i> <u>=====</u>
		<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			
		<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			
		<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			
		<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			
		<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			
		<small>Pres Rad FL</small>			

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A577

Date: 18/9/97

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓			Approx 0568
	REF -	7	2853	✓			Approx 2858
	AOSS	19	0000		F/S TORQUE 4.5		2047 st. and level
	AOA	18	0000		F/S TORQUE 3.0		2047 st. and level
	RD HT	37	0000				As Indicated 0000
	PR HT	8	3801	100			As Altimeter
	CABP	14	3321	1000			
	A/S	9	0005	✓			As ASI 0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	0004		JCID		
	UP2S	82	0000				
	UIRS	83	0075		JNOL		
	UP1Z	84	0008		JCID		Approx 0147
	UP2Z	85	0045	✓			Approx 0149
	UIRZ	86	0070		JNOL		Approx 2061
	UP1T	87	0074		JCID		As IAT
	UP2T	88	2405	✓			As IAT
	UIRT	89	0000		JNOL		As IAT
	LP1S	91	0080		JCID		
	LP2S	92	0010				
	LIRS	93	0005		JNOL		
	LP1Z	94	0070		JCID		Approx 0150
	LP2Z	95	0040	✓			Approx 0146
	LIRZ	96	0005		JNOL		Approx 2050
	LP1T	97	0000		JCID		As IAT
	LP2T	98	2205	✓			As IAT
	LIRT	99	0000		JNOL		As IAT
	J/W	42	0000	0			As Indicated 0000
	HYGR	58	3000	+20			
	HYCC	59	0015	✓			696-901
	FDEW	138	2200	10			DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C
	FSTA	139	0000				
	DTF	10	2000				
	DTC	11	0				
	NDTF	23	0000				same as De-Iced
	NDTC	24	0				
	INCT	48	2743				
	HEIM	141	3110				
	PRTC	142	2000	✓			approx 2380
	TWCD	70	3750	✓			0000-4094
	TSAM	72	0000	✓			0640-1860 < min
	O3	100	0000				
	O3P	106	0000				$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$
	O3RG	113	1000				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	0577	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0093			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0245			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	8			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3754	1492 3856	3755	048d	3757	3683	3752	0158 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	0000			Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	0000			Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 0

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	3671	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	1459	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	01A9	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2721	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2276	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	2072	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	2572	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1028	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	048d			4095	
	EV1V	170	2072				
	EV2V	171	2072				
	NPWR	172	3230				
	EVIC	173	3968				
	EV2C	174	3968				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOME	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear J01D	Off / On	Large / Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon J117		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear J01D	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon J117		

Flight Leader's Pre In-Flight Check List

Flight No:

Date:

18/9/97

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CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓		Approx 0568	
	REF -	7	2853	✓		Approx 2858	
	AOSS	19	1871		F/S O/S TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1978		F/S O/S TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	1605	7500'		As Indicated 0000	
	PR HT	8	2409	✓	8000'	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	2505	755			
	A/S	9	2741	260		As ASI 0000 - 0100	
	UP1S	81	0563		J01D		
	UP2S	82	1764				
	UIRS	83	0848		JN0L		
	UP1Z	84	0566		J01D	Approx 0147	
	UP2Z	85	0764	✓	J01D	Approx 0149	
	UIRZ	86	0852		JN0L	Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	1805		J01D	As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2501	✓		As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0200		JN02	As IAT	
	LP1S	91	1597		J01D		
	LP2S	92	0412	✓			
	LIRS	93	2408		JN0L		
	LP1Z	94	1728		J01D	Approx 0150	
	LP2Z	95	0649	✓		Approx 0146	
	LIRZ	96	0451		JN02	Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	0875		J01D	As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2824	✓		As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0200		JN0L	As IAT	
	J/W	42	0861	0.0		As Indicated 0000	
	HYGR	58	2115	-11			
	HYCC	59	0765	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1721	-13		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	0608				
	DTF	10	3339	13			
	DTC	11	5				
	NDTF	23	3154	13		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	5				
	INCT	48	2526				
	HEIM	141	2524				
	PRTC	142	2382	✓		approx 2380	
	TWCD	70	0928			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	1188			0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0167				
	O3P	106	1708			$P \approx (DRSU \times 0.4) + 145mB$	
	O3RG	113	2157				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	877			Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0113			Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0226			Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	13			Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
3254 1548	3857 020725	3255	0700	3256	3708	3257	0167 ✓
	LATC	160	Dec	0452	38N		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	3785	27W		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection

Height: 9000'

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70	0874	✓		0001-4095	
	TNOS	71	2858	✓		2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72	1145	✓		0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73	2780	✓		2400-3200	
	TSRC	74	2246	✓		2160-2470	
	HTR1	75	1714	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76	1077	✓		0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77	1025	✓		0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78	4095	✓		4095	
	EV1V	170	2442				
	EV2V	171	3138				
	NPWR	172	2670				
	EVIC	173	4001				
	EV2C	174	4007				

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear	Off / On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear	Off / On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 577.....

Date 15/9/97.....

Page 1 of 2.....

Video Tape	
No. A577#1	A577#2
Ends 1404	1632
(FC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	36 58.36N	36 58.36N
Long	025 09.96	025 09.90
Time	0214	0230
Status	S ₂	GL AUGN

DRS recording to HORACE	(y) / n
HORACE recording to disc	(y) / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	(y) / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
081016			DATA		ON				
107715			SET		INU TO	NAV			NOTE FOR DAT.
105835			T/O		SANTA	MANUA			ON CO. HORACE O/P 433 PPB
110447	9		START UNDO		A577#1	CANT=200			START READ 44PPB AND - 4PPB START READ 0.0.
111311	10	FL80		315	180				CONSTANT CORRECTION ARE -70 & 0.48PPB CHANGED TO -16 & 0.48PPB
112419	11	FL80		315	185				
133046	14								END TAPE AS 77#1 CANT=200 ON HOR. CALIB. DAT
133221	15								START TAPE AS 77#2 CANT=200
134302	16	FL200		195		START RUN 2			
140001	17	FL200		200		END RUN 2 / START P1			WRF IS ONE SECOND FASTER THAN P3
140651	18	FL40		010		END P1			
140801	19	FL40		010		START RUN 3			
142301	21	FL40				END RUN 3 / START P2			
143039	22	FL70		200		END P2			
143401	23	FL70				START RUN 4			
144401	25	FL70		210		END RUN 4 / START P3			
145608	26	1000'		015		END P3			
145701	27	1000'		015		START RUN 5			
151501	28	1000'		015		END RUN 5			
151817	29	1015'	1015	310		START PROFILE P4.1			SS=5
152837	30	FL100		320		END P 4.1			
153005	31	FL100		180		START RUN 6			
153257	32	FL100				END RUN 6 / START P4.1			

© Research Flight

NOTE WRF CLOCK IS ONE SECOND FASTER THAN P3

Video Tape	
No.	AS77#2
Ends	1632 AS77#3 1933
(FFC) / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat		
Long		
Time		
Status		

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ / n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ / n
SATCOM sending pos reports	☒ / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/Sea st.
154433	33	FL200		170	END P4.2				
155714	34	FL200		170	START P5				
155837	35	FL185		170	INTERUPT P5 - BOTTLE FILL				185, 165
160439	36	FL185		175	RESTART P5 ↓				185, 165
160654	37	FL165		175	INTERUPT P5 - BOTTLE FILL				115, 80
161118	38	FL165		175	RESTART P5				
161910	39	FL185		175	INTERUPT P5 - BOTTLE FILL				
162307	40	FL190		180	RESTART P5 ↓				
162652	41	5000'		180	END P5 - BOTTLE FILL				
162845	42	5000'		175	START P6 ↑				
163257	43				END UNDER AS77#2 (QNH) = 6016				
163337	44				START UNDER AS77#3 (QNH) = 6000				
163403	45	FL185		170	INTERUPT P6 - BOTTLE FILL				FL80
163554	46	FL180		170	RESTART P6				
164402	47	FL165		170	INTERUPT P6				
164814	48	FL158		170	RESTART P6 A				
165231	49	FL200		170	END INTERUPT P6 - BOTTLE FILL				
165817	50	FL200		170	START P7 ↓				170, 120
170016	51	FL180		170	INTERUPT P7 - BOTTLE FILL				50
170421	52	FL180		170	RESTART P7				
170559	53	FL166		170	INTERUPT P7 - BOTTLE FILL				
170932	54	FL166		170	RESTART P7				
171404	55	FL170		170	INTERUPT P7 - BOTTLE FILL				
171627	56	FL170		170	RESTART P7 ↓				
172226	57	FL150		135	INTERUPT P7				
172637	58	FL150		130	RESTART P7				
172953	59	2000'		130	INTERUPT / END P7 - BOTTLE FILL				
173144	60	2000'		130	START P8 ↑				
17445	61	FL150		130	INTERUPT P8				
174229	62	FL150		130	RESTART P8				1000/min
175152	65	FL137		130	INTERUPT P8 - ALL BOTTLE				500/min
175551	66	FL135		130	RESTART P8				
175657		FL1250		130	END P8 - FILL BOTTLE				

Research Flight

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. 577

Date 18 9 97

Sheet no. 1/1

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run no. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
1	H12			FL 200	134305	134545	135037	469	INTERCOMP 5.7 bar RUN 1
2	R31			FL 200	135149	135701	135902	469	5.8 bar 2
3	R6			FL 140	140720	141200	141320	598	7.0 bar 3
4	R11			FL 140	141440	141920	142100	598	7.0 bar 3
5	R39			FL 70	142800	143440	143717	785	1440 1445 7.0 bar. RUN 4
6	R7			FL 070	143900	144100	144150	784	7.0 bar 4
7	R35			1000'	150625	150115	150550	979	7.0 bar 5
8	R30			1000'	150400	150805	150835	979	7.0 bar 5
9	R24			1000'	151040	151203	151233	979	Extra bottle. 7.0 bar 21 5
10	R5			FL 185	155910	160250	160431	497	(20 left. 188 PS) 5.5 bar 19 PS
11	R40			FL 165	160620	160950	161113	540	6.0 bar 19 PS
12	H9			FL 87	161900	162213	162255	732	6.8 bar 18

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

Flight No. 577 Date 18 9 97 Sheet no. 2

Sample no.	Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run No. etc.)
					PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
13	R2			FL 050	162425	162958	163033	846	7 bar ON P5
14	R29			FL 80	163200	163520	163538		7 bar 17 16 P6
15	H2			FL 158	164300	164555	164758	554	6.5 bar 15
16	R23			FL 200	164915	165537	165810	467	5.3 bar 14
17	R 28			FL 180	165900	170145	170414	508	6.0 bar 13 n180 n20 50 V
18	R 10			FL 164	170540	170700	170923	542	6.5 12
19	R 34			FL 120	171100	171515	171623	646	7 bar 11
20	H06			FL 50	171720	172601	172635	845	7 bar 10
21	R1			2000'	172800	172953 173110	173140	957	7 bar 9
22	H01			FL 234 2000'	173400	175152 175340	175547 175600	483	AT LEVEL 8 4.5 bar 200
23	R8			FL 250	175720	175930	180052	307	3.9 bar 7
24	R21			FL 210	180222	180520	180760	450	5 bar 6 n180 110
25	R17			FL 110	181030	181500 181735	181834	674	AT LEVEL 7 bar 12/15/10

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A577

DATE: 18/9/97

MRF | AC.SOE

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION:			
GPS	✓	✓	
OMEGA	✓	✓	
INU	✓	✓	
RADALT	✓	✓	
THERMOMETERS:			
DI TEMP	✓	✓	
NDI TEMP	✓	✓	
ICTP	✓	✓	
HEIMANN	✓	✓	
HYGROMETERS:			
GEN. EASTERN	✓	✓	
TWC	✓	✓	
FWVS	✓	✓	
J/W	✓	✓	
EXP. PITOT HEAD:			
STATIC PRESS.	✓	✓	
PITOT PRESS.	✓	✓	
GUST VANES	✓	✓	
RADIOMETERS:			
UPPER CLEAR	✓	✓	2011)
UPPER RED	✓	✓	
UPPER SILICON	✓	✓	JNO ₂
LOWER CLEAR	✓	✓	5011)
LOWER RED	✓	✓	
LOWER SILICON	✓	✓	JNO ₂
MARSS	X		
SAFIRE	X		
DEIMOS	X		
ARIES	X		
CHEMISTRY:			
OZONE	✓	✓	
ECGC	✓	✓	
NOX	✓	✓	
OTHERS:			
CCN	X		
CLOUD PHYSICS	X		
CABIN PRESS	✓	✓	
NEPHELOMETER	X		
PSAP	✓	✓	

P.T.O. FAULTS/INCIDENTS

DATE 18 SEP 97	FTI No 01/02	FLT No A 577	NAV AYERS
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD SANTA MARIA	ATIS 2/18	200/08	H 1021
ATC CLEARANCE JULIET 3 4 /35 3707 2753 F080			TAKE OFF TIME 1059

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1113 ¹¹	291	Ø	290	254	295	298/05	F080	1021	3717.6	02554.9	R1
1124 ¹⁹									3744.1	02648.1	ER1
1343 ⁰⁰	181	Ø	251	197	224	211/29	F200		4409.8	03534.8	R2
1400 ⁰¹									4258.0	03535.0	ER2/P1
1406 ⁵¹											EPI/R2
1408 ⁰¹						210/25	F140		4249.8	03541.5	R3
1423 ⁰¹									4357.4	03541.5	ER3/P2
1430 ³⁹							F070				EP2
1434 ⁰¹	185	1P	204	198	225	214/19	✓		4328.2	03551.3	R4
1449 ⁰¹									4236.6	03559.8	ER4/P3
1456 ⁰⁸											EP3
1457 ⁰¹	358	2S	227	204	213	188/23	F010		4301.6	03606.5	R5
1515 ⁰¹									4409.4	03606.7	ER5
1518 ¹⁷						154/20	50'	1014	4419.0	03614.4	P4.1
1528 ³⁷									4436.9	03703.1	EP4/P1
1530 ⁰³	165	Ø	PP	180	204	177/14	F100		4434.5	03707.0	R6
1532 ⁵⁷									4425.2	03703.2	ER6/P4.2
1544 ³³									4349.0	03642.7	EP4.2
1557 ¹⁴	151	6P	236	255		210/34			4307.7	03604.5	P5
1558 ³⁷							F185		4303.3	03600.5	IP5
1606 ⁵⁴							F165		4235.9	03539.0	IP5
1619 ¹⁰							F088		4157.4	03510.7	IP5
1626 ⁵⁴						207/18	F050		4134.9	03455.8	EP5
1630 ⁴³							A		4124.4	03448.3	P6
1634 ⁰³							F085/F080		4115.6	03441.5	IP6

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME
ATC CLEARANCES	TAKE OFF
ATIS	FLIGHT TIME

3321050 16 ~~100~~ 1050 5 10 : 54

DATE	FTI No	FLT No	NAV
DEPARTURE AIRFIELD		ATIS	
ATC CLEARANCE			TAKE OFF TIME 1059

TIME	FIN 1012			IAS	TAS	W/V	ALT FL	QNH	GPS		RUN IDENT
	HDG	DR	G/S						LAT/LONG		
1644 ⁰²	154	9P	200	180	234	221/26	F165/188	1021	4045.5	03418.8	1P6
1652 ³¹							F200		4018.0	03356.6	EP6
1658 ¹⁷							↘		3958.1	03340.7	P7
1700 ¹⁶						222/26	F180		3951.3	03335.4	1P7
1705 ⁵⁹						217/22	F164		3932.1	03320.9	1P7
1714 ⁰⁴						197/17	F120		3905.7	03301.1	1P7
1723 ²⁶						218/19	F050		3847.5	03227.5	1P7
1729 ⁵⁷						197/14	F020		3839.9	03202.3	EP7
1731 ⁴¹						198/14	↗		3837.8	03155.6	P8
1751 ⁵²							F237/F235		3809.0	03027.7	1P8
1756 ⁵⁷							F250		3758.9	03000.3	EP8
1801 ⁰²									3751.0	02939.7	P9
1803 ⁰¹							F210		3747.2	02929.8	1P9
1814 ⁴³							F110		3726.1	02836.1	EP9
1818 ³⁸	119	3P	222	182	221	229/13	F110		3719.6	02819.8	R7
1830 ²¹									≈ 3707.0	02726.4	EP7

ARRIVAL AIRFIELD	LANDING TIME 1901
ATC CLEARANCES & F050	TAKE OFF 1059
ATIS 100/04 101L F020 B035 23 1021	FLIGHT TIME 8.00

A577

GPS data
08:11:48 - 19:06:24

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
✓	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log <i>BOTTLES</i> ✓
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log. ? Photographic log (photocopy original)
✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

ASXN EGRR SURFACE DT 0000 UTC 18 SEP 1997 97408

METEOLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F20

** TOTAL PAGE.001 ** MET-OFFICE_ARTIFRX_4 PAGE.001

18 SEP 197 07:56

Approved for Release by the Central Intelligence Agency on 09-08-2013 pursuant to E.O. 13526, Declassify on: OADR

18 SEP '97 04:02

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METEOLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F 28

** TOTAL PAGE:001 **

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4 PAGE.001

18 SEP '97 04:02

Prepared and drawn by the Cartographic Section, METO, 18th, Brixham, UK. (Carto) O Item File:1168

Amended July 1998

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 0000 UTC 19 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20M

Prepared and drawn in the Cartographic Section, RMO/ISA, Enderbury
Met. Office, 1000 from files
Approved July 1996

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

18 SEP '97 16:54

FS/FUXX EGRR

POL STER. PROJ. STAND. PARALLEL 60°N 0 500 1000 NM SEA LEVEL ISOPLETHS 1000-500mb THICKNESS ISOPLETHS

T+72 VT 00Z SUN 21 SEP 1997 18 SEP '97 06:35 ** TOTAL PAGE.001 ** MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_4 PAGE.001

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FS/FUXX EGRR

METEOROLOGICAL OFFICE FAX F12A

18 SEP '97 06:51

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** TOTAL PAGE:001 **

and time in the Cartographic System, Met.O.100, British

Met.O.(Cell.D.O.(Form File)) (Revised May 1988)

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MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX-2 PAGE.001

18 SEP '97 04:06

ILAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03:36:10 CHART 27 PHDA50 EGRR 0000Z

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

I + 24

GMAIN

19/ 9/97

VT 00Z FRI

00Z THUR 18/ 9/97

PHDE50 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 27

LAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.44.19

LOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TAL PPN RATE
ESSURE AT MSL

T+0 VI OZ THURSDAY 18/9/1997

OW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TAL PPN RATE
ESSURE AT MSL

OT 00Z THURSDAY 18/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

.03 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VT

T+12 VT 12Z THURSDAY 18/9/1997

18 SEP '97 03:27

MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_3

PAGE. 001

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

DT 00Z THURSDAY 18/9/1997 LMAIN

OW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TAL PPN RATE
ESSURE AT MSL

I+24 WT 0Z FR/DAY 19/9/1997

OW PROBABILITY AT MSL
 TAL PPN RATE
 ESSURE AT MSL

01 00Z THURSDAY 18/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW CONVECTIVE DYNAMIC
 MM/HR AT VT

0.03 .1 .5 1.0

I+36 VT 12Z FRIDAY 19/9/1997

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

.03 .1 .5 1.0 MI/HR AT V1

LOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE

LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 050

VALID 12 UTC 18 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE

UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'

DATA TIME 12 UTC 17 SEP 97

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON
CHART FOR FL 100
VALID 12 UTC 18 SEP 97
TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 17 SEP 97

99315

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 180

VALID 12 UTC 18 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 17 SEP 97

EGRR 1200Z

99314

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 240

VALID 12 UTC 18 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY .PS.
DATA TIME 12 UTC 17 SEP 97

EGR 1200Z

99313

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 300

VALID 12 UTC 18 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'

DATA TIME 12 UTC 17 SEP 97

ECRA 1200Z

A580 21-SEP-97

P1 FL210 FL180 (133126-133445) + P2 FL180-FL210 (135524-140230)

A580 21 - SEP - 97

P3 FL270-FL102 R/FL239/FL205/FL121/FL102(160408-163302) + P4 FL102-FL270 R/FL164/FL199/FL230/FL250/FL270(163718-171416)

A580 21-SEP-97

P6 FL270-FL150 R/FL150(171450-172355) + P6 FL150-FL270 R/FL196/FL227/FL270(172640-174612)

A577 18-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 111311-112419 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:33

A577 18-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 111311-112419 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:34

A577 18-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 111311-112419 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:34

A577 18-SEP-97 R1 FL80 From 111311-112419 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:34

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 669
 Mean 753.759
 Standard dev 0.514798
 Max value 755.377
 Min value 751.798

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 669
 Mean 283.073
 Standard dev 0.219397
 Max value 283.478
 Min value 282.681

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 669
 Mean 263.821
 Standard dev 3.72046
 Max value 268.094
 Min value 255.570

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 669
 Mean 57.2541
 Standard dev 4.88277
 Max value 67.9011
 Min value 46.5401

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 669
 Mean 1.000000e-38
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 1.000000e-38
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 669
 Mean 14.1827
 Standard dev 0.540052
 Max value 15.4950
 Min value 13.3245

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 669
 Mean 2426.34
 Standard dev 5.44575
 Max value 2447.10
 Min value 2409.24

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 669
 Mean 37.5217
 Standard dev 0.135505
 Max value 37.7374
 Min value 37.2945

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 669
 Mean -26.3940
 Standard dev 0.262687
 Max value -25.9169
 Min value -26.8040

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 669
 Mean -1.72915
 Standard dev 0.452011
 Max value -0.700035
 Min value -2.90718

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 669
 Mean 1.50578
 Standard dev 0.520486
 Max value 2.68436
 Min value 0.119850

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 669
 Mean -8.770625e-02
 Standard dev 0.364730
 Max value 0.688461
 Min value -0.786819

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 669
 Mean 2.34855
 Standard dev 0.465286
 Max value 3.39005
 Min value 1.03835

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 318.950

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 669
 Mean 140.902
 Standard dev 18.8613
 Max value 155.223
 Min value 107.477

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 302.077

A577 18-SEP-97 R2 FL200 From 134301-140001 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:42

A577 18-SEP-97 R2 FL200 From 134301-140001 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:42

A577 18-SEP-97 R2 FL200

From 134301-140001 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:42

A577 18-SEP-97 R2 FL200 From 134301-140001 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:42

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 467.403
 Standard dev 0.118110
 Max value 467.773
 Min value 467.019

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 257.567
 Standard dev 0.315543
 Max value 258.567
 Min value 257.024

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 247.906
 Standard dev 1.82660
 Max value 253.852
 Min value 243.312

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 59.3774
 Standard dev 2.51550
 Max value 71.1866
 Min value 53.4393

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 1021
 Mean 1.000000e-38
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 1.000000e-38
 Min value 1.000000e-38

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 15.5233
 Standard dev 0.937401
 Max value 18.7167
 Min value 14.2410

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 6068.29
 Standard dev 1.83966
 Max value 6074.27
 Min value 6062.52

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 43.5707
 Standard dev 0.344964
 Max value 44.1670
 Min value 42.9740

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1021
 Mean -35.5822
 Standard dev 8.464256e-04
 Max value -35.5807
 Min value -35.5836

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 11.9969
 Standard dev 0.633370
 Max value 13.6732
 Min value 10.5660

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 8.24427
 Standard dev 0.440139
 Max value 9.44404
 Min value 6.83710

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 8.163647e-03
 Standard dev 0.341347
 Max value 0.794266
 Min value -1.05735

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 14.5614
 Standard dev 0.673404
 Max value 16.4383
 Min value 12.7942

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 214.497

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1021
 Mean 142.064
 Standard dev 0.962826
 Max value 144.931
 Min value 140.030

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 180.075

A577 18-SEP-97 P1 FL200 FL140 From 140001-140651 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:47

A577 18-SEP-97 P1 FL200 FL140 From 140001-140651 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:47

A577 18-SEP-97 P1 FL200 FL140 From 140001-140651 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:47

A577 18-SEP-97 R3 FL140 From 140801-142301 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:54

A577 18-SEP-97 R3 FL140 From 140801-142301 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:54

A577 18-SEP-97 R3 FL140 From 140801-142301 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:54

A577 18-SEP-97 R3 FL140 From 140801-142301 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:54

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 899
 Mean 596.541
 Standard dev 0.116080
 Max value 596.899
 Min value 596.234

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 899
 Mean 270.634
 Standard dev 0.326539
 Max value 271.134
 Min value 269.585

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 899
 Mean 245.658
 Standard dev 5.81024
 Max value 271.042
 Min value 238.589

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 899
 Mean 81.2669
 Standard dev 9.29010
 Max value 94.7066
 Min value 54.6236

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 899
 Mean 1.927089e-07
 Standard dev 1.876035e-06
 Max value 1.892652e-05
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 899
 Mean 13.4047
 Standard dev 0.332735
 Max value 14.2194
 Min value 12.8333

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 899
 Mean 4250.47
 Standard dev 1.48429
 Max value 4254.40
 Min value 4245.89

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 899
 Mean 43.3931
 Standard dev 0.326886
 Max value 43.9592
 Min value 42.8282

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 899
 Mean -35.6936
 Standard dev 8.942173e-04
 Max value -35.6919
 Min value -35.6960

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 899
 Mean 10.0991
 Standard dev 0.604419
 Max value 11.7108
 Min value 8.81305

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 899
 Mean 4.52081
 Standard dev 1.34790
 Max value 7.38378
 Min value 1.94481

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 899
 Mean 7.361803e-02
 Standard dev 0.319034
 Max value 0.936836
 Min value -0.784958

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 899
 Mean 11.1391
 Standard dev 0.728236
 Max value 13.7016
 Min value 9.49382

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 204.115

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 899
 Mean 129.483
 Standard dev 1.18361
 Max value 132.193
 Min value 126.335

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 5.979650e-02

A577 18-SEP-97 P2 FL140 FL70 From 142301-143039 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:56

A577 18-SEP-97 P2 FL140 FL70 From 142301-143039 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:56

A577 18-SEP-97 P2 FL140 FL70 From 142301-143039 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:56

A577 18-SEP-97 R4 FL70 From 143401-144901 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:58

A577 18-SEP-97 R4 FL70 From 143401-144901 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:58

A577 18-SEP-97 R4 FL70 From 143401-144901 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:58

A577 18-SEP-97 R4 FL70 From 143401-144901 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:58

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 901
 Mean 782.233
 Standard dev 0.220894
 Max value 782.831
 Min value 781.516

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 901
 Mean 282.083
 Standard dev 0.426374
 Max value 282.797
 Min value 281.269

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 901
 Mean 275.241
 Standard dev 1.22540
 Max value 279.027
 Min value 271.652

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 901
 Mean 56.8562
 Standard dev 3.06319
 Max value 63.9078
 Min value 47.4057

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 901
 Mean 7.634017e-07
 Standard dev 7.560966e-07
 Max value 2.734292e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 901
 Mean 11.6394
 Standard dev 1.04518
 Max value 13.7062
 Min value 8.03706

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 901
 Mean 2129.67
 Standard dev 2.26746
 Max value 2137.03
 Min value 2123.53

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 901
 Mean 43.0368
 Standard dev 0.249179
 Max value 43.4707
 Min value 42.6106

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 901
 Mean -35.9062
 Standard dev 3.664330e-02
 Max value -35.8552
 Min value -35.9980

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 901
 Mean 8.03027
 Standard dev 0.758834
 Max value 9.39021
 Min value 6.41884

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 901
 Mean 4.49096
 Standard dev 0.956325
 Max value 6.59990
 Min value 2.52376

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 901
 Mean -6.063310e-02
 Standard dev 0.180460
 Max value 0.480347
 Min value -0.613068

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 901
 Mean 9.27415
 Standard dev 0.364535
 Max value 10.1184
 Min value 8.30513

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 209.216

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 901
 Mean 115.619
 Standard dev 2.18343
 Max value 118.727
 Min value 106.198

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 186.968

A577 18-SEP-97 P3 FL70 1000' From 144901-145608 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:59

A577 18-SEP-97 P3 FL70 1000' From 144901-145608 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:59

A577 18-SEP-97 P3 FL70 1000' From 144901-145608 Plotted 7-May-1998 16:59

A577 18-SEP-97 R5 1000' From 145701-151501 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:04

A577 18-SEP-97 R5 1000' From 145701-151501 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:04

A577 18-SEP-97 R5 1000' From 145701-151501 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:04

A577 18-SEP-97 R5 1000' From 145701-151501 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:05

A577 18-SEP-97 R5 1000' From 145701-151501 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:05

A577 18-SEP-97 R5 1000'

From 145701-151501 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:05

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 1079
Mean 976.592
Standard dev 0.269603
Max value 977.111
Min value 975.511

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 1079
Mean 292.885
Standard dev 0.284040
Max value 293.603
Min value 292.147

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 1079
Mean 291.348
Standard dev 0.395650
Max value 292.305
Min value 290.152

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 1079
Mean 36.6535
Standard dev 1.76861
Max value 40.5600
Min value 30.2025

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 1079
Mean 3.888563e-06
Standard dev 3.155845e-06
Max value 1.280864e-05
Min value 9.514374e-07

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 1079
Mean 9.42515
Standard dev 1.06998
Max value 11.5474
Min value 4.95731

RADAR HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 1079
Mean 332.698
Standard dev 3.27646
Max value 344.997
Min value 326.422

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1079
Mean 43.5943
Standard dev 0.326559
Max value 44.1574
Min value 43.0273

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 1079
Mean -36.1099
Standard dev 1.203847e-03
Max value -36.1081
Min value -36.1132

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1079
Mean 9.84529
Standard dev 0.773005
Max value 11.8621
Min value 8.61024

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1079
Mean 0.437609
Standard dev 1.06219
Max value 2.72877
Min value -1.82750

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 1079
Mean 0.144366
Standard dev 0.262349
Max value 1.34683
Min value -0.652084

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 1079
Mean 9.90825
Standard dev 0.820099
Max value 11.9290
Min value 8.61183

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 182.545

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 1079
Mean 106.260
Standard dev 1.43648
Max value 110.007
Min value 102.666

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 359.853

A577 18-SEP-97 P4.1 50' FL100 From 151817-152837 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:07

A577 18-SEP-97 P4.1 50' FL100 From 151817-152837 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:08

A577 18-SEP-97 P4.1 50' FL100 From 151817-152837 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:08

A577 18-SEP-97 R6 FL100 From 153003-153257 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:09

A577 18-SEP-97 R6 FL100 From 153003-153257 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:09

A577 18-SEP-97 R6 FL100 From 153003-153257 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:09

A577 18-SEP-97 R6 FL100 From 153003-153257 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:09

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 175
 Mean 694.737
 Standard dev 0.293691
 Max value 695.937
 Min value 694.541

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 175
 Mean 275.024
 Standard dev 0.150616
 Max value 275.483
 Min value 274.836

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 175
 Mean 270.537
 Standard dev 1.33902
 Max value 271.942
 Min value 266.110

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 175
 Mean 57.2563
 Standard dev 1.36241
 Max value 61.5229
 Min value 54.3518

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 175
 Mean 4.461673e-07
 Standard dev 3.881608e-07
 Max value 1.232298e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 175
 Mean 14.0465
 Standard dev 0.337192
 Max value 14.5015
 Min value 13.5493

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 175
 Mean 3071.42
 Standard dev 3.31675
 Max value 3073.64
 Min value 3057.87

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 175
 Mean 44.4971
 Standard dev 4.586188e-02
 Max value 44.5750
 Min value 44.4180

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 175
 Mean -37.0854
 Standard dev 1.873454e-02
 Max value -37.0528
 Min value -37.1175

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 175
 Mean 7.23064
 Standard dev 0.391192
 Max value 8.37428
 Min value 6.51926

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 175
 Mean 0.461549
 Standard dev 0.359300
 Max value 1.47264
 Min value 3.082275e-03

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 175
 Mean -1.878021e-02
 Standard dev 0.328837
 Max value 0.497238
 Min value -0.867844

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 175
 Mean 7.25333
 Standard dev 0.407313
 Max value 8.49575
 Min value 6.56784

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 183.652

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 175
 Mean 111.185
 Standard dev 1.60107
 Max value 113.224
 Min value 107.940

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 163.564

A577 18-SEP-97 P4.2 FL100 FL200 From 153227-154433 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:12

A577 18-SEP-97 P4.2 FL100 FL200 From 153227-154433 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:12

A577 18-SEP-97 P5 FL200 5000' R/FL185/FL165/FL88/5000' From 155714-162652 Plotted 7-May

A577 18-SEP-97 P5 FL200 5000' R/FL185/FL165/FL88/5000' From 155714-162652 Plotted 7-May

A577 18-SEP-97 P5 FL200 5000' R/FL185/FL165/FL88/5000' From 155714-162652 Plotted 7-May

A577 18-SEP-97 P6 5000' FL200 R/FL85/FL165/FL200 From 163043--165231 Plotted 7-May-1998

A577 18-SEP-97 P6 5000' FL200 R/FL85/FL165/FL200 From 163043-165231 Plotted 7-May-1998

A577 18-SEP-97 P6 5000' FL200 R/FL85/FL165/FL200 From 163043-165231 Plotted 7-May-1998

A577 18-SEP-97 P7 FL200 2000' R/FL180/FL164/FL120/FL50/2000' From 165817-172953 Plotted

A577 18-SEP-97 P7 FL200 2000' R/FL180/FL164/FL120/FL50/2000' From 165817-172953 Plotted

A577 18-SEP-97 P7 FL200 2000' R/FL180/FL164/FL120/FL50/2000' From 165817-172953 Plotted

A577 18-SEP-97 P8 2000' FL250 R/FL150/FL237/FL250 From 173141-175657 Plotted 7-May-1998

A577 18-SEP-97 P8 2000' FL250 R/FL150/FL237/FL250 From 173141-175657 Plotted 7-May-1998

A577 18-SEP-97 P8 2000' FL250 R/FL150/FL237/FL250 From 173141-175657 Plotted 7-May-1998

A577 18-SEP-97 P9 FL250 FL110 R/FL210/FL110 From 180102-181443 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:4

A577 18-SEP-97 P9 FL250 FL110 R/FL210/FL110 From 180102-181443 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:4

A577 18-SEP-97 P9 FL250 FL110 R/FL210/FL110 From 180102-181443 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:4

A577 18-SEP-97 R7 FL110 From 181838-183025 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:46

A577 18-SEP-97 R7 FL110 From 181838-183025 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:46

A577 18-SEP-97 R7 FL110 From 181838-183025 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:46

A577 18-SEP-97 R7 FL110 From 181838-183025 Plotted 7-May-1998 17:46

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 708
 Mean 671.415
 Standard dev 0.206778
 Max value 671.975
 Min value 671.026

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 708
 Mean 277.609
 Standard dev 0.403220
 Max value 278.364
 Min value 276.969

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 708
 Mean 255.202
 Standard dev 2.27835
 Max value 260.021
 Min value 250.068

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 708
 Mean 63.4734
 Standard dev 4.53534
 Max value 72.1689
 Min value 56.6927

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 708
 Mean 9.466596e-07
 Standard dev 1.493001e-06
 Max value 5.127713e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 708
 Mean 7.22893
 Standard dev 0.180963
 Max value 7.68125
 Min value 6.91965

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 708
 Mean 3338.60
 Standard dev 2.40211
 Max value 3343.12
 Min value 3332.09

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 708
 Mean 37.1861
 Standard dev 6.691145e-02
 Max value 37.3279
 Min value 37.1178

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 708
 Mean -27.9071
 Standard dev 0.251261
 Max value -27.4572
 Min value -28.3307

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 708
 Mean 2.96971
 Standard dev 0.521193
 Max value 4.30080
 Min value 1.70187

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 708
 Mean 4.42541
 Standard dev 0.893804
 Max value 6.19582
 Min value 2.61121

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 708
 Mean -0.152047
 Standard dev 0.256041
 Max value 0.457916
 Min value -1.32940

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 708
 Mean 5.34248
 Standard dev 0.965244
 Max value 7.30190
 Min value 3.25830

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 236.136

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 708
 Mean 113.645
 Standard dev 1.54787
 Max value 120.207
 Min value 110.615

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 106.710

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.

Particle Data

- **CNC:** Condensation nucleus counter (this data is provisional and requires further validation). The measurement is from a commercial instrument: TSI INC Model 3025A. Although CNC data were recorded on the flight no post flight processing has been carried out. Rather than delay this booklet further, I have decided to wait and process the data when the validation has been carried out by the cloud physics group.
- **PSAP:** The Radiance Research Particle Soot Absorption Photometer gives a measurement of optical absorption by black carbon, using a quartz filter with the absorption measured at 565 nm.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent and Ken Dewey (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (data not quality controlled). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data (approx) converted to ppb using approximate scale factor and offset. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_{y1}) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in bits. Only one NO_y channel was available for this flight. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section) to see when these were filled. Analysis carried out at NILU.
- **CO:** Approximate data in ppb from the DRS. Instrument scientist: Sandra Schmitgen (fz-Jülich).

ARASF

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